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**The main directions of socio-economic
development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions**

MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
JIZZAKH BRANCH OF THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF UZBEKISTAN
NAMED AFTER MIRZO ULUGBEK

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The main directions of socio-economic development of New Uzbekistan:
problems and solutions collection of materials of the international scientific
and practical conference on the topic

(May 6, 2024)

Jizzakh-2024

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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2. Jizzakh branch of the National university of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
3. Kazan Federal University (Russia)
4. Fast support and result LLC
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INTRODUCTION

In our country, large-scale work is carried out on the modernization of the higher education system, the introduction of modern forms and technologies of education, the improvement of the directions of training specialists. In the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, important issues of radical updating the content of Personnel Training, creating the necessary conditions for the training of highly qualified specialists on the basis of international templates are outlined. At the moment, special attention is paid to the development of the material and technical base of the Institute.

Science and innovative research in it are at the center of these changes and serve as catalysts for progress in various fields such as the exact and natural sciences, economics, Information Technology, social and humanities, and so on. The main goal in the idea of the new Uzbekistan is to open new opportunities for solving and developing technologies and current social problems by investing in research and innovation.

The problems waiting for their solution to improve the effect of reforms in this direction carried out in our republic, create conditions for the comprehensive and rapid development of the state and society, modernize our country and liberalize all spheres of life will find their solution in the process of discussions, discussions and scientific lectures between high-potential scientific schools. The conference will discuss the results of advanced fundamental and Applied Research, increasing the intellectual prestige of our country and commercializing the results of research.

The main purpose of the conference is to develop scientifically based proposals for the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, solve the tasks facing production enterprises, educational institutions and also other industry organizations by proposing new innovative solutions, studying potential solutions. In addition, the conference aims to synchronize the results of scientific research carried out in educational institutions and research institutes. Through the Scientific Reports at our conference, we are looking forward to opening a new path for young researchers, doctoral students and very talented students to communicate with the scientific community.

As a result of the conference, the environment of mutual scientific and creative cooperation between professors, students, scientific worker-researcher, independent researcher, scientists and specialists of related fields and the exchange of feedback and experience will be created, which will be combined on the path of development of Science and technology. The conference also provides for the active promotion of the intellectual prestige of our country and the commercialization of the results of research. In short, we believe that the rapid implementation of such processes as having practical skills in the training of mature qualified specialists, gaining experience, developing the modern educational process and establishing systematic work on linking new teaching processes to industry professionals will be an impetus for us to achieve great heights.

It should be noted that special attention is paid to the reform of the educational system, the conditions being created for young people, the emergence of their abilities and talents, the formation of loyalty. After all, loyalty to the Fatherland, el-yurt, is a great virtue.

YANGI O'ZBEKISTON — YOSHLARGA YANGI IMKONIYATLAR ESHIGI

International
scientific and
practical conference

Xojiboqiyeva Nigina O'tkir qizi

O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining Jizzax filiali talabasi

Abstract

About 20 percent of the world's population are young people, and the politics, economy, and culture of every country, and of course today and tomorrow, are related to them. And in Uzbekistan, this figure exceeds 60 percent. Young people are the hope of every nation, and creating the necessary conditions for each of them to acquire knowledge and start their own entrepreneurship through youth policy is among the urgent issues that every country has to face. The decree of the head of our state on July 5, 2017 "On improving the effectiveness of the state policy on youth and supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" brought the work in this regard to a new stage.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "Any task related to the future of young people is of primary importance."

Keywords

Policy, initiative, principle, intellectual, entrepreneurship, current, complex, entrepreneurship, internet, privilege, content, value, spiritual, priority, universal, youth, innovative, youth parliament, project factory, initiative.

Аннотация

Около 20 процентов населения мира составляют молодые люди, и с ними связана политика, экономика и культура каждой страны, и, конечно, сегодня и завтра. А в Узбекистане эта цифра превышает 60 процентов. Молодые люди —

надежда каждой нации, и создание необходимых условий для того, чтобы каждый из них приобретал знания и начал собственное предпринимательство посредством молодежной политики, входит в число неотложных задач, с которыми сталкивается каждая страна. Указ главы нашего государства от 5 июля 2017 года «О повышении эффективности государственной политики в отношении молодежи и поддержке деятельности Союза молодежи Узбекистана» вывел работу в этом направлении на новый этап.

Шавкат Мирзиёев: «Любая задача, связанная с будущим молодежи, имеет первостепенное значение».

Ключевые слова:

Политика, инициатива, принцип, интеллектуальный, предпринимательство, текущий, комплексный, предпринимательство, интернет, привилегия, содержание, ценность, духовный, приоритет, универсальный, молодежный, инновационный, молодежный парламент, фабрика проектов, инициатива.

Annotatsiya

Dunyo axolisining qariyb 20 foizi yoshlar bo'lib har bir davlatning siyosati, iqtisodiyoti, madaniyati hamda albatta bugungi va ertangi kuni ular bilan bog'liq. Shuningdek O'zbekistonda esa bu ko'rsatkich 60 foizdan oshadi. Yoshlar har millatning umidi bo'lib, aynan yoshlar siyosati orqali ularning har biriga bilim olish, o'z tadbirkorligini yo'lga qo'yish uchun kerakli shart-sharoitlarni yaratish har bir davlat oldiga qo'ygan dolzarb masalalar qatoridadir. Davlatimiz rahbarining 2017 yil 5 iyuldagi «Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati samaradorligini oshirish va O'zbekiston yoshlar ittifoqi faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash to'g'risida»gi farmoni bu boradagi ishlarni yangi bosqichga olib chiqdi.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev: "Yoshlar kelajagi bilan bog'liq har qanday vazifa birlamchi ahamiyatga ega."

Kalit so'zlar:

Siyosat, tashabbus, printsip, intellektual, tadbirkorlik, dolzarb, kompleks, tadbirkorlik, internet, imtiyoz, kontent, qadriyat, ma'naviy, ustuvor, umuminsoniy, yoshlar, innovatsion, yoshlar parlamenti, loyihalar fabrikasi, tashabbus.

Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatining asosiy printsiplari

Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatining asosiy printsiplari quyidagilardan iborat:

- ochiqlik va shaffoflik;
- yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini ro'yobga chiqarishda yoshlarning ishtirok etishi;
- yoshlar tashabbuslarini qo'llab-quvvatlash va rag'batlantirish;
- ma'naviy, axloqiy va madaniy qadriyatlarning ustuvorligi;
- yoshlarning kamsitilishiga yo'l qo'yilmasligi.

Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatining asosiy yo'nalishlari

Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatining asosiy yo'nalishlari quyidagilardan iborat:

- yoshlarning huquqlari, erkinliklari va qonuniy manfaatlarini ta'minlash;
- yoshlarning hayoti va sog'lig'ini saqlash;
- yoshlarning ma'naviy, intellektual, jismoniy va axloqiy jihatdan kamol topishiga ko'maklashish;
- yoshlar uchun ochiq va sifatli ta'limni ta'minlash;
- yoshlarni ishga joylashtirish va ularning bandligi uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish;
- yoshlarni vatanparvarlik, fuqarolik tuyg'usi, bag'rikenglik, qonunlarga, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga hurmat ruhida, zararli ta'sirlar va oqimlarga qarshi tura oladigan, hayotga bo'lgan qat'iy ishonch va qarashlarga ega qilib tarbiyalash;
- yoshlarni axloqiy negizlarni buzishga olib keladigan xatti-harakatlardan, terrorizm va diniy ekstremizm, separatizm, fundamentalizm, zo'ravonlik va shafqatsizlik g'oyalaridan himoya qilish;
- yoshlarning huquqiy ongi va huquqiy madaniyati darajasini yuksaltirish;
- iqtidorli va iste'dodli yoshlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash hamda rag'batlantirish;
- yoshlar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish;
- yoshlarda sog'lom turmush tarziga intilishni shakllantirish, shuningdek yoshlarning

bo'sh vaqtlarini mazmunli tashkil etish va yoshlar sportini ommaviy rivojlantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish;

– yosh oilalarni ma'naviy va moddiy jihatdan qo'llab-quvvatlash, ular uchun munosib uy-joy va ijtimoiy-maishiy sharoitlarni yaratish bo'yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar tizimini amalga oshirish;

– yoshlarning huquqlari va erkinliklarini ro'yobga chiqarish sohasida faoliyatni amalga oshiruvchi xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlikni rivojlantirish.

Davlatimiz rahbarining ham yoshlar forumida yoshlar kelajagi bilan bog'liq har qanday vazifa birlamchi ahamiyatga ega ekanini alohida ta'kidladi.

“– Yoshlar bilan ishlash Prezidentdan tortib vazirgacha, hokimdan tortib mahalla raisigacha – hammamizning eng asosiy ishimizga aylanishi zarur. Har qaysi hokim, har bir vazir, har qaysi mahalla raisi “Bugun men yoshlar uchun nima ish qildim? Ertaga farzandlarimiz manfaati uchun yana nima ish qilishim kerak?” degan savollarga javob beradigan, shunday e'tiqod bilan yashaydigan vaqt keldi.”

Xususan, oliy ta'lim muassasalari soni salkam uch marta ko'payib, qamrov darajasi 9 foizdan 38 foizga yetgani zamonaviy ilm va kasb sohalarini egallashda yoshlar uchun yangi imkoniyatlar ochmoqda. Oxirgi uch yilning o'zida 250 ming nafar yoshga 6 trillion so'mdan ziyod imtiyozli kreditlar ajratildi. Mamlakatimiz bo'yicha 210 ta “Yoshlar sanoat va tadbirkorlik zonalari” tashkil etilib, 4 trillion so'mlik 2,5 mingta loyiha amalga oshirildi. Natijada, yosh tadbirkorlar soni 2 karra ko'payib, 200 mingdan oshdi. Yuqoridagi ta'kidlardan ham ko'rinib turibdiki yoshlarga bo'lgan e'tibor shunchaki bir xalqning avlodlarini yetishtirish emas, balki ayni bir siyosiy mavzu sifatida qaralib davlatning kelajagini qurish uchun qo'ygan qadami ekanini yaqqol namoyoni ekanligi olg'a surilmoqda. Aynan yoshlarning sportda hamda ta'limda uzviy ravishda o'zlarini ko'rsatishiga yo'llarning ochilishi, mana shu sohalarda yetakchi o'rinlarni egallashimizga birlamchi omil bo'lib kelmoqda. Bundan tashqari yoshlarning loyihalarini moliyalashtirish maqsadida alohida jamg'arma tashkil etilib 100 million dollar mablag' ajratildi.

Yoshlarning bilim olishi uchun yaratilayotgan imkoniyatlar hech kimga sir emas, misol tariqasida kontrak asosida o'qishga kirganlar uchun talaba krediti tashkil etilganligi, qizlar uchun foizsiz talaba kreditini borligi, magistratura to'lovlarini esa qizlar uchun davlatimiz tomonidan to'lab berilishini keltirishimiz mumkin. Bundan tashqari xorijiy tillarni yaxshi o'zlashtirgan o'quvchilarni rag'batlantirish maqsadida 70 nafar o'quvchilarni ustozlari bilan birgalikda Buyuk Britaniyaga safarga yuborish katta bir imkoniyatdir. Ha bir davlat oldida turgan katta muammolardan biri bu o'qishni bitirgan yoshlarni bandligini ta'minlashdir. Shuning uchun ham Prezidentimiz yoshlarning bandligini ta'minlash masalasiga alohida e'tibor qaratdi. **Tadbirkorlik dasturlariga 220 ming nafar, kasb-hunar o'rganishga 130 ming nafar, davlat korxonalari va xususiy sektordagi bo'sh ish o'rinlariga 110 mingdan ziyod o'g'il-qizlar** jalb etilishi ta'kidlandi. Kelgusida Internet tarmog'ida O'zbek milliy kontentini rivojlantirish dasturi amalga oshirish, bu maqsadlar uchun **10 milliard so'm mablag'** yo'naltirish alohida maqsad qilib olindi.. Undan tashqari malaka oshirish uchun yoshlarga ish o'rinlarini yaratilishi uchun tashkilotlarga turli imtiyozlarning yaratilishi ham bu muammoga alohida e'tibor ramzidir. Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini izchil va samarali amalga oshirish, yoshlarni har tomonlama qo'llab-quvvatlash, huquq va qonuniy manfaatlarini himoya qilish tizimini tubdan isloh etish, yoshlar sohasidagi muammolarga samarali yechimlar ishlab chiqish, vakolatli organlar faoliyatini samarali tashkil etish va muvofiqlashtirish maqsadida O'zbekiston yoshlar ittifoqi hamda Yoshlar ishlari agentligi tashkil etildi. Bundan tashqari, Oliy Majlis Senatida Yoshlar, madaniyat va sport masalalari qo'mitasi, Oliy Majlisi Qonunchilik palatasida Yoshlar masalalari bo'yicha komissiya, Oliy Majlis palatalari huzurida "Yoshlar parlamenti" tashkil qilindi. Shu bilan birga Innovatsion rivojlanish vazirligi qoshida Yoshlar akademiyasi tashkil etildi. Hududlarda "Loyihalar fabrikasi" ish boshladi. Mazkur ishlar natijasida O'zbekiston yoshlar ittifoqi tashkil topgandan buyon 841 147 nafar yoshning bandligi ta'minlandi. 2021-yilning birinchi yarmida Yoshlar ishlari agentligi tomonidan 78 140 nafar yosh ishga joylashtirilgan bo'lib, 5 684 nafar yoshga subsidiyalar ajratildi, ijtimoiy himoyaga muhtoj 127 nafar talabaning 350 million so'mlik to'lov shartnoma mablag'lari

to'lab berildi. Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosatini amalga oshirishda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti tomonidan ilgari surilgan besh muhim tashabbusni targ'ib qilish va ro'yobga chiqarish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Mazkur g'oyani amalga oshirish maqsadida O'zbekiston yoshlar ittifoqi qoshida "5 tashabbus loyiha ofisi" faoliyati yo'lga qo'yildi. Tegishli loyihalar, jumladan, "Sport karvoni", "Bir million dasturchi", "Eng yaxshi kitobxon oila" kabi loyihalar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Turli sohalarda samarali faoliyat yuritayotgan, yuqori natijalarga erishib, tengdoshlariga o'rnak bo'layotgan yigit-qizlarni rag'batlantirish maqsadida "Mard o'g'lon" davlat mukofoti va "Kelajak bunyodkori" medali ta'asis etildi. O'tgan vaqt davomida 113 nafar yosh "Mard o'g'lon" davlat mukofoti bilan, 75 nafari esa "Kelajak bunyodkori" medali bilan mukofotlandi. Bundan tashqari har yili 8-mart arafasidagi bayram dasturida 28 nafar qiz va ayollarimizga "Zulfiya" nomidagi davlat mukofotini Prezidentimizning shaxsan o'zlari topshirishlari yoshlar siyosatini samarali amalga oshayotganligi ifodasidir.

Xulosa qilib aytganda biz yoshlarga bo'lgan e'tibor, davlatimiz rahbarining bizlarga qarata "Men sizlarga ishonaman" degan ishonchlari yuqori marralarni egallashimiz uchun bir dasturi amal yaratishimiz uchun asos bo'la oladi. Mana shunday imkoniyatlardan unumli foydalanganlar qatorida men ham borligim, va "Zulfiya" nomidagi davlat mukofotini qo'lga kiritishim kelajakda oldimga qo'ygan maqsadlarimni tubdan o'zgartirib yuborni deya olaman. Ushbu mukofot nafaqat rag'bat balki Prezidentimiz, yurtimizni menga qaratgan e'tibor va ishonchi ramzi deb qabul qildim. Shuning uchun ham ulkan bir mas'uliyat bilan qabul qildim. Yoshlarni kamol topishi, e'tibor va e'tirofga sazovor bo'lishi bir so'z bilan bir davlatda yoshlarning qadr topishi deya mana shu imkoniyat va yutuqlarni hech ikkilanmay ayta olishimiz mumkin.

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